

**DESCRIPTION OF A NEW SPECIES OF *OCENEBRA* (MURICIDAE:
OCENEBRINAE) FROM WESTERN AFRICA.**

Roland Houart*

Introduction:

In the course of the revision of Recent species of the family Muricidae in Western Africa, available collections are examined or reexamined. The material collected since more than 5 years in the Gulf of Guinea and Angola revealed many interesting species, of which a new *Ocenebra* is here described. Several *Muricopsis* (*Risomurex*) spp. and other species are still being studied and the results of the investigations will be made known in the final revision.

Ocenebra coseli n. sp.

figs. 1-2, 5-6

Type material: Holotype MNHN, 30 paratypes from the type locality deposited in following collections: MNHN (12), Centro de Zoologia do IICT, Lisboa (5); IRSNB (2); Natal Museum, Pietermaritzburg (2); coll. R. Houart (9).

Type locality: Cape Esterias, Pointe Idolo, Gabon, low tide, under stones in sand, R. v. Cosel coll. 14 Nov. 1985 (21 spms); P. Bernard coll. 1986 (9 spms).

Distribution: From Gabon (Cape Esterias) to North of Angola.

Material examined: The type material and several specimens from Gabon (type locality) and northern Angola (Barra do Dande, prov. Bengo, 0-2 m, MNHN and Cabo Ledo, prov. Luanda, 10-40 m, MNHN).

Dimensions:

Holotype: 9.3 × 4.1 mm

Paratypes: from 8.5 to 13 mm in height.

Description: Shell small, solid and fusiform. Spire high and acute, consisting of 3.2 protoconch whorls and 5 to 6 teleoconch whorls. Protoconch whorls with strong median keel. First teleoconch whorls bearing strong, non spinose, axial varices, and weak spiral cords. Last whorl bearing 3 rounded varices and a strong intervarical axial ridge. Spiral sculpture consisting of 5 to 6 cords and 3 to 4 squamous intermediate finer threads. Aperture small, elongate and regularly ovate. Columellar

* St. Jobstraat 8, B-3330 Landen (Ezemaal) Belgium. Scientific Collaborator at the Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique.

lip smooth, adherent to the shell. Inner side of outer apertural lip bearing 4 to 5 shallow denticles. Anal notch narrow and deep, delimited by a small callus on its inner edge. Siphonal canal straight, ornamented with 2 to 3 spiral cords; narrowly open.

Color dark brown to almost bluish-black; spiral cords lighter coloured where they cross the varices. Aperture dark.

Radula typical for the subfamily, with a rachidian tooth and 2 lateral denticles. Rachidian with a short central cusp, 2 long lateral and marginal cusps and a series of smaller denticles.

Discussion: *Ocenebra coseli* is related to *Ocenebra isaacsi* Houart, 1984 and *Ocenebra inermicosta* (Vokes, 1964). The three species live sympatrically at Cape Esterias (Gabon) where *O. coseli* is the commonest of the three and at Barra do dande (Angola) where *O. isaacsi* is the commonest.

O. coseli and *O. isaacsi* have both a multispiral and keeled protoconch, a character only observed in these two West African Ocenebrinae and which probably indicates a very near relationship. *O. isaacsi* has a finer and more squamous sculpture; the apertural anal notch is broad and looks like some of the Bursidae; the outer apertural lip is more wingshaped and the whorls are more angulate.

O. inermicosta has a rounded multispiral protoconch with two weaker spiral cords. Adult specimens of *O. inermicosta* reach a length of 33 mm for 6 to 7 teleoconch whorls; the aperture is larger and the siphonal canal is partially closed.

The species is named for Rudo von Cosel who collected the first specimens made available to me.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I thank Dr. A. Warén (Stockholm) who mounted the radula and Dr. P. Bouchet (MNHN) for SEM work, Mr. P.A. Bernard (Gabon) for specimens and Dr. P. Bouchet and Prof. E.H. Vokes (Tulane University) for reading the manuscript.

FIGURES

Figs. 1-2: *O. coseli* n. sp. holotype MNHN, 9.3 × 4.1 mm

Fig. 3: *O. inermicosta* (Vokes, 1964), Gambia, R. Houart coll., 33 × 14.2 mm

Fig. 4: *O. isaacsi* Houart, 1984, Gabon, R. Houart coll., 13 × 7.1 mm

Fig. 5: Radula of *O. coseli*, Cape Esterias, MNHN, (scale: 10 μ)

Fig. 6: Protoconch of *O. coseli* (scale: 0.5 mm)

Fig. 7: Protoconch of *O. inermicosta* (scale: 0.5 mm).

6

7

